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BRIDGES

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Introduction

The agroBRIDGES project proposes the development of an agri-food multi-actor framework and a set of practical support tools to connect producers and consumers in new business and marketing models for Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs), as these are a straightforward way to improve local producers' market position and decrease intermediaries margin.

Specifically, while there are still unfair trade conditions, mild incentives and complex relationships with consumers, agroBRIDGES will allow producers to fully exploit their potential by empowering them with knowledge that will support better decision making, improved relationships with contracting authorities and consumers, strategic alliances creation (i.e. farmers competitiveness increase and growth).

To raise awareness of the relevance of Short Food Supply Chains and local food in our society, this handbook is aimed at educational institutions and consumers. It has been divided into two main sections:

1 **Diving into basic concepts: this section provides you with all the relevant information you need to know about Local food, Short Food Supply Chains, and healthy diets.**

2 **Raising awareness while inspiring others: this section has been designed to provide you with the skills you need when training others and give you some tips to carry out knowledge transfer activities**

Apart from these sections, you will find customisable communication materials that can be used in training activities for kids and adults, and relevant information corresponding to different beacon regions.

Abbreviations

B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
EU	European Union
RDP	Rural Development Programmes
SFSCs	Short Food Supply Chains

SFSCs & local food in Europe

SFSCs & local food in Europe

Understanding SFSCs

The Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs) in the EU are part of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and their promotion through legal and policy incentives implemented since 2014, in the framework of national Rural Development Programmes (RDP) (agroBRIDGES Consortium, 2021).

The definition of what constitutes a Short Food Supply Chain remains unclear amongst academics and policymakers, but it's widely understood as "a supply chain that has a limited number of economic actors, committed to co-operation, local economic development, and close geographical and social relations between producers, processors and consumers" (EU, 2013).

•Local food

It "is produced within a short distance of where it is consumed, often accompanied by a social structure and supply chain different from the large-scale supermarket system".

•Short food supply chains (SFSCs)

For the purposes of the agroBRIDGES project a definition was developed and agreed that is clear and easy to understand: Short food supply chains have as few links as possible between the food producer and the consumer/citizen who eats the food.

•Consumer

"A person who buys goods or services for their own use"

•Supply Chain

It can be defined as the "entire system of producing and delivering a product or service, from the very beginning stage of sourcing the raw materials to the final delivery of the product or service to end-users".

As explained in the key concepts section, for the agroBRIDGES project a clear and easy to understand definition was developed: short food supply chains have as few links as possible between the food producer and the consumer/citizen who eats the food. It improves local producers' market position and decreases intermediaries' margin, it makes it possible to have fresher products, with lower distribution costs, and a fairer remuneration for the producer.

·Food producer

A “person who grew, raised, processed, prepared, manufactured, or otherwise added value to the food product the person is selling”.

·Fresh

When used with fruit and vegetables, it means that have not been processed (e.g. canned, pickled, preserved or frozen).

SFSCs are identified as a more sustainable way of producing, processing, and/or selling food which demonstrates a 'turn to quality' in both agriculture and consumption. SFSCs can be understood as supply chains related to 'sales in proximity' in the sense that locally grown or produced foods are served to local consumers, where the number of intermediaries is minimised. The ideal being that there is direct contact between the producer and the consumer, while increasing the revenue/income for farmers/producers.

There exists different types of SFSCs: on-farm sales, farmers' markets, internet deliveries, box delivery, pick-your-own and community supported agriculture (CSA), among others .

The importance of this model relies on its contribution "to a more positive, fair, healthy and sustainable development path" (Strength2food project, 2020) and its capability to bring economic, social and environmental benefits.

•Sales in proximity

This model captured both face-to-face methods (consumer buys directly trusting in personal interaction) or Proximate short food supply chains (food is produced and sold in a given region of production).

•Farmers' market

It is "a physical retail marketplace where farmers can sell their home-grown produce, as well as other processed goods, directly to consumers".

SFSCs & local food in Europe

Kumpulainen et al. (2018) stress the role SFSCs play socially and economically at a community level to facilitate rural development. The very values and meanings attributed to SFSCs and their origin can develop a sense of pride, social cohesion and belonging (Peters, 2012). In addition, SFSCs can therefore animate local social life where markets can even become a meeting place for local people.

SFSCs also increase, or help re-circulate, community income and create new jobs (Peters, 2012; Wittman, Beckie and Hergesheimer, 2012).

The SMARTCHAIN (2021) and the STRENGTH2FOOD (2021) project have summarised the different benefits of SFSCs in the following images:

Figure 2. Economic benefits of SFSCs

Figure 3. Social benefits of SFSCs

Figure 4. Environmental benefits of SFSCs

The above is a compilation of general benefits found to be achieved through several different SFSCs, but it does not mean that every SFSC will deliver them.

In addition, the benefits of SFSCs contribute to different Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as can be seen in the following image .

SDGS LINKED TO SFSCS

1 NO
POVERTY

2 ZERO
HUNGER

5 GENDER
EQUALITY

8 DECENT WORK AND
ECONOMIC GROWTH

9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION
AND INFRASTRUCTURE

11 SUSTAINABLE CITIES
AND COMMUNITIES

12 RESPONSIBLE
CONSUMPTION
AND PRODUCTION

13 CLIMATE
ACTION

Understanding local food

Local food is that “produced within a short distance of where it is consumed, often accompanied by a social structure and supply chain different from the large-scale supermarket system ” (Waltz, 2011). This is in line with the abovementioned definition of SFSCs as it implies that there are few links between the food producer and the final consumer.

In a review of SFSC studies, Feldmann and Hamm (2015) concluded that trust in the food supply chain and the belief that local food is healthier, are important factors supporting SFSCs. Freshness and healthfulness are among the most relevant characteristics for consumers (Kvam and Bjørkhaug, 2015).

The agroBRIDGES project conducted a survey in different regions and the findings suggest that the major motivation for consumers purchasing SFSC products is “quality attributes of the product in terms of taste, freshness and healthiness”.

SFSCs are linked in different ways to local agriculture and local food (United Nations Industrial Development Organization, 2020). It should be highlighted that SFSCs are not only about local food as this concept focuses on “ensuring production, processing, trade and consumption all occur within a defined geographical boundary, without limiting the stages, or considering anything further than the location of the actors involved”. This means, that even if many times SFSCs are local food markets, SFSCs are not only about local food.

Local food is considered healthy as it normally uses “less of inputs such as pesticides, synthetic fertilisers, animal feed, water and energy” (Augère-Granier, 2016). These characteristics do not imply only a health benefit but also an environmental one, as local food normally needs less packaging and less energy for storage when compared to food sold in supermarkets.

Linked to the benefits of SFSCs, the following advantages are associated with local food:

Each one of these advantages is discussed in detail below in order to provide an overview of how important SFSCs are for our society and why we should keep supporting them. Specific examples from different countries, extracted from a study carried out in the agroBRIDGES project, are included to help you better understand how you could benefit from buying local food from SFSCs.

High-Quality, fresh, and healthy products

For many consumers, SFSCs represents a means to access high quality, fresh, locally sourced products and they are willing to adopt these supply chains in their decision-making and purchasing processes (Elghannam et al, 2019). SFSCs normally deliver raw products, such as vegetables, fruits, and organic food which, as will be explained in the next section, are basic products to have a healthy diet.

There is already strong evidence that consumers associate local food with good taste, freshness, purity, and positive environmental value (Pelto-Huikko, 2013). This is an argument dominant in Mediterranean countries such as Greece, where local food is often perceived as a safe and environmentally friendly option.

The nutritional aspects linked to a greater freshness of the products, the attention of producers in communicating the healthy use of raw materials and social trends of a healthy lifestyle are also promoting the consumption of local food from SFSCs in countries such as Italy, Lithuania or Poland.

Additionally, in France, the successive health crises (mad cow disease, avian and swine flu, COVID-19) are increasing the attractiveness of SFSCs and the demand for local and organic supplies.

It should also be mentioned that globalised food chains also alter the concept of seasonality, which is largely recognised as a key component of sustainable and healthy diets. In general terms, the 'localness' of food is connected to 'healthiness' by association with freshness, seasonality and affordability (Belletti, 2020)

•Healthy diets

“Healthy diets have an optimal caloric intake and consist largely of a diversity of plant-based foods, low amounts of animal source foods, contain unsaturated rather than saturated fats, and limited amounts of refined grains, highly processed foods and added sugars”.

Product knowledge, transparency and traceability

Consumers perceive data about methods of production, farmer information and social values of producers as an added value that enhances their consumption preferences (Galli et al, 2013).

A Finnish study revealed that more and more consumers are making informed choices for ethical and responsible food production. The best option for consumers who have concerns for the health of their environment would be to purchase local products that are in season, from producers who use ecologically sound production methods or are certified, organic producers.

It's important to understand that food, specifically fruits and vegetables, start to lose their nutrients in the first 24 hours of being picked, and that is why local food offered in SFSCs many times is fresher and contains plenty of nutrients. Furthermore, SFSCs offer food that is not normally exposed to chemical products or other artificial conditions as they are not intended for long-distance transport.

The decision of many consumers towards buying local food from SFSCs is supported by the fact that local producers can be trusted, and that the traceability of the product is appreciated. Consumers have access to more accurate information when meeting the people who grow the food, and it should be noted that “local farmers typically focus on soil health and safe growing practices, especially if they’re farming organically, and these practices typically mean better tasting and more nutritious produce ” (Amisson, 2022)

In Italy, thanks to the SFSC models, consumers can directly learn about the production methods used and have a direct perception of the aspects that the producers value most, by visiting the farms or speaking directly to the producers.

•Farming

It is “the activity of growing crops or keeping animals on a farm

Convenience/efficiency/ease of access

As will be later explained, consumers can access local food through different channels and select the most appropriate one according to their circumstances and preferences.

For example, in the Netherlands, according to Tacken et al. (2021), supermarkets are the main sales channel for SFSC products followed by other channels such as Hotels, Restaurants and Cafes (HoReCa), and farm shops.

In Denmark, traditional channels such as outdoor markets in the cities and farm shops are experiencing a new boom and these are complemented by newer business models like meal boxes and online sales, while in Italy, the box scheme delivered through the use of bicycles, is the predominant sales channel.

E-commerce is an example of a growing SFSC in countries such as Finland or Denmark. That trend has accelerated during the COVID-19 crisis and is particularly driven by new customers coming in and trying to buy food online for the first time (Danish Agriculture & Food Council).

•Farm shop

“A retail outlet which sells produce directly from a farm”.

•Box scheme

“An arrangement where consumers pay a fixed amount for an agreed quantity of vegetables, fruit or other produce, to be delivered to their home on a regular basis”

A different outlook is found in Latvia where some SFSCs are part of traditional lifestyles in rural communities and partly in cities. Farmers' markets are the most common. Self-consumption and self-production models are a norm in many households, especially in rural communities and any excess production is sold directly to customers, that are normally friends, neighbours, and relatives, thus creating micro-SFSCs.

In Turkey, products are sold to local marketers, greengrocers and food/beverage businesses in wholesale markets, eventually reaching consumers through these businesses.

In each country, there are different options available to consumers wanting to access local food through SFSCs and each of the options brings its own advantages and disadvantages as is explained in the "Finding local food in SFSCs" section.

• Wholesale

"The business of selling of goods in large quantities and at low prices, typically to be sold on by retailers at a profit".

Producer-consumer interactions (social benefits)

When consumers buy local food coming from SFSCs social interactions are occurring which brings benefits for the society as a whole.

SFSCs allow for the creation of greater trust between producers and consumers and strengthen the sense of community. There is evidence that SFSCs play an important role in local societies in the region by favouring the interaction and connection between farmers and consumers, thus promoting the development of trust.

Models such as Solidarity Purchasing Groups imply the active participation of consumers, coalescing them around a common goal. Models such as the Farmers Market, on the other hand, allow the exchange and convergence of objectives between different producers interested in attracting consumers.

•Solidarity purchasing group

“A group of people, e.g. households, that co-operate in purchasing food and other produce directly from farmers”.

Furthermore, this interaction and connection relates to social values, ensuring quality products to consumers at fair prices. For example, in Greece consumers want to support local production for environmental and ethical (fair trade or support to the local economy) reasons.

In Finland and France, the production of local food builds social capital through cooperation and creating trust between different actors, which in turn increases the demand for local food and improves marketing opportunities (Glowacki-Dudka et al., 2012). Factors highlighted by customers who consume local foods include fairness, interaction, community spirit and trust, and these can be regarded as social capital for local food companies (LähiSos, 2017).

For consumers, local food is also associated with interaction with the food producer, usually a small local producer. Consumers appreciate the story and experientiality associated with local food. The storytelling is often associated with the area's food traditions and culture, which consumers are proud of and want to maintain (Pelto-Huikko, 2013).

In Italy, the presence of a good level of associationism (associations, consortia, cooperatives, collective logos, etc.) supports the development of SFSCs and increases access to local food. The smoother connection between producers and consumers allows for the strengthening of symbolic, informative, perceptive connections between the city and the countryside.

In larger Danish cities, food communities are perceived as completely new access to local products, bringing with it a very close relationship between producers and consumers.

SFSCs have a significant impact on reducing inequalities between regions as product suppliers (farmers) usually operate in rural areas, while consumers operate in large cities. As a result, cash flow shifts from rich to poor regions, helping to boost consumption and create jobs in poorer regions. This has a positive effect on the reduction of internal migration from villages and small towns to large cities.

As an example, in Denmark, the food cluster's production, directly and indirectly, gives rise to the employment of 189,000 people, corresponding to 6.3% of total Danish employment. In rural municipalities, 12.8% of jobs are associated with the food cluster's production.

Finding local food in SFSCs

As part of the agroBRIDGES project, different SFSCs business and marketing models have been identified to provide an overview on how consumers can access local food through SFSCs.

The chain of activities that take place in the entire process from food production to delivery to the final consumers shapes the food supply chain. Across various stages of the chain, different actors are involved to fine-tune the outcome, offering and adding value to the whole food supply chain (i.e, farmers, processors, distributors, and retailers).

This section aims to illustrate the business models identified in the framework of the agroBRIDGES project and highlight the different channels available in each one of them, as well as their advantages and disadvantages. In this way, consumers have the opportunity to analyse and decide how to access local food.

Retailer

“A person or business that sells goods to the public in relatively small quantities for use or consumption rather than for resale”.

Community Supported Agriculture (CSA)

In this case, local consumers act as co-owners and there is normally a partnership with local supermarkets and farm shops. Producers and consumers have a pre-existing agreement where consumers pay an agreed membership fee or offer labour services (or both), in exchange for production.

Weekly deliveries are also one of the characteristics of this business model that uses the following channels to reach consumers:

- On-farm pick up
- Central distribution site
- Farmer's market distribution
- Home delivery
- Bulk distribution

Reasons to choose these channels

- High-quality food for a local community using sustainable farming methods
- Direct seller recommendations available for a more personal approach
- Delivering fresh and healthy food while increasing community identification
- Wide variety of products rather than a large quantity
- First-hand experience, product knowledge and traceability
- Producer-consumer interaction
- High quality, fresh and healthy food

Reasons not to choose these channels

- Consumers may feel overwhelmed when receiving a large amount of varied food
- Higher prices when compared to standard markets

•Community supported agriculture

Abbreviated CSA, it is a partnership model between consumers and producers "where partly share part of the risks, decisions and rewards of production". Both sides obtain different benefits as stable and secure incomes, and access to fresh food.

•Local community

Group of people within a local geographical area

Face-to-face

Producers are selling their products directly to customers, improving transparency and trust, and minimising food waste. Even if the subscription model is also available, the primary channels include:

- sales directly on-site or close to production locations
- special events and fairs, farm events
- open-air markets, local markets

Why to choose these channels

- Wide range of local products
- Direct information available about the origin of the products and cultivation conditions
- High-quality of products, fair prices and easy accessibility
- First-hand experience product knowledge and traceability
- Producer-consumer interaction
- High quality, fresh and healthy food available

Why not to choose these channels

- Irregular supply
- High prices
- Need to match already established schedules with personal time availability

Food waste

It “refers to good quality food fit for consumption that is consciously discarded at the retail and consumption stages”.

Local Food Trade

In this model, local products are available for customers with healthy and organic products at convenient locations. Various channels form part of this model:

- Specialized stores and marketplaces
- Marketplaces with intermediary enrolment
- Collective outlets of local farmers
- Small specialized local shops
- Dedicated spot at supermarkets

Reasons to choose these channels

- Consumers can purchase all local products from one place.
- Direct information available about food source
- Access to quality products at fair and reasonable prices
- First-hand experience, product knowledge and traceability
- Producer-consumer interaction
- High quality and healthy products available

Reasons not to choose these channels

- No regular order placement
- Small flexibility as ordered products are delivered in certain locations at certain times

Intermediary

a person or organization who passes proposals between two people or groups.

Local shop

“An independent local business which sells products within a local community”.

Online Food Trade

This includes online platforms that trade and deliver farming goods to ensure that citizens can access local and natural goods from sustainable and socially oriented sources. There are also subscription options to boost engagement.

Through these different channels, this model also benefits medium and large cities as it allows local and farmers' markets to connect with end-users:

- E-commerce platform and website
- Pick-up or delivery boxes
- Delivery vehicles for urban rides
- Collaboration and distribution networks

Reasons to choose these channels

- Time flexibility, online tools, and platforms make it easy to order local organic food
- Delivery at home or business locations (ease of consumption)
- Quick, reliable method of ordering
- Citizens can access local and natural goods from sustainable and socially oriented sources
- High quality and healthy products

Reasons not to choose these channels

- No direct information available about food source
- No direct contact with the producer

More information about SFSCs in the different geographical areas has been summarised in the 12 factsheets found in Annex I.

In addition, 51 success cases have been gathered from different countries across Europe to disseminate approaches that have been proven to work so that end-users can identify what is appropriate for their own circumstances and capacities. These success cases are a good way to understand how consumers are interacting with SFSCs and the benefits they are obtaining. They can be found on the agroBRIDGES website.

Improved logistics

The last business model identified in the agroBRIDGES project corresponds to improved logistics and is based on the unification of packaging, to reduce transportation costs and the involvement of intermediaries such as transport companies or parcel services.

The abovementioned business models addressed diverse customer segments, most of them targeting individual consumers, small shops or groups. However, this model targets B2B and B2C customer segments, meaning that consumers are not only individual users but also groceries and healthy food shops, canteens at workplaces, companies, schools, or universities.

There is a cooperation between producers to develop a joint entity to enhance transport & packaging

Reasons to choose these channels

- High-quality standards guarantee product freshness
- The transport of food is made by a company specialised in organic food and products with a short shelf life
- Competitive prices
- Traceability of food quality and food origin

Reasons not to choose these channels

- Food distributed in specific centres and locations
- No direct seller recommendations available

Benefits of healthy diets

Benefits of healthy diets

Once SFSCs and their connection with local food has been understood, the next step is to learn about the benefits of healthy diets.

As explained in the key concepts section, a healthy diet has an “optimal caloric intake and consists largely of a diversity of plant-based foods, low amounts of animal source foods, contains unsaturated rather than saturated fats, and limited amounts of refined grains, highly processed foods and added sugars ” (EAT-Lancet Commission , 2019).

A healthy diet should not be understood as something very specific and directly applicable to all individuals as it can vary from person to person depending on age, geographical and demographical conditions, and other individual characteristics. In addition, the benefits of a healthy diet can also vary between adults and children.

In Figure 1, the Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (2021) have summarised the main benefits a healthy diet brings to adults and children. Most of the benefits are the same while others are related to specific situations dependent on age.

•Plant-based food

It includes fruits, vegetables, nuts, seeds and whole grains.

BENEFITS OF HEALTHY EATING for Adults

May help you **live longer**

Lowers risk of heart disease, type 2 diabetes, and some cancers

Keeps **skin, teeth, and eyes** healthy

Supports **healthy pregnancies and breastfeeding**

Supports **muscles**

Helps the **digestive system** function

Boosts **immunity**

Strengthens **bones**

Helps achieve and maintain a **healthy weight**

BENEFITS OF HEALTHY EATING for Children

Keeps **skin, teeth, and eyes** healthy

Supports **brain development**

Supports **muscles**

Supports **healthy growth**

Helps achieve and maintain a **healthy weight**

Boosts **immunity**

Strengthens **bones**

Helps the **digestive system** function

The benefits for adults can be put into two groups; those focused on preventing diseases and those intended to improve health, which in the long run also prevents health issues:

1

Diseases prevention : Healthy food helps you to maintain an adequate weight, which in many cases is a risk factor for disease. A healthy diet could have multiple benefits, protecting your body against conditions such as “obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, some types of cancer and skeletal conditions” (World Health Organization, 2021)

●**Heart disease:** the kind of food consumed can have a direct impact on our blood pressure, which could lead to a heart attack or other types of heart diseases. Different studies indicate that it is possible “to prevent up to 80% of premature heart disease and stroke diagnoses with lifestyle changes, such as increasing physical activity and healthful eating .” (Crichton-Stuart, 2020)

●**Cancer risk:** This can be diminished in two ways: antioxidants contained in specific foods could protect cells from damage, and reducing consumption of saturated fats or foods with high amounts of added sugar can prevent some cancers including gastrointestinal tract cancers.

●**Bone issues:** food with high amounts of calcium and magnesium helps to improve bone strength, minimising the risk of diseases such as osteoporosis.

2

Improve your overall health: apart from preventing disease, healthy food impacts other aspects of your personal life:

● **Mood:** Some studies have shown that the type of food you eat can have an impact on symptoms of depression and fatigue. For example, a diet with a high glycemic load could increase symptoms depression and fatigue.

● **Brain health:** the brain can benefit from a healthy diet as it can improve memory and maintain cognition.

● **Sleeping:** reducing intake of saturated fats, alcohol or caffeine will improve quality of sleep

● **Gut health:** the food you eat could help good bacteria thrive in the colon, making it easier to carry out its role in metabolism and digestion.

All the above explains why numerous international institutions, public authorities and governments are putting effort into raising awareness about the importance of adopting healthy habits, especially when it is related to our food consumption. These efforts are often translated into national policies, nutritional plans, and financing opportunities, among others.

As the agroBRIDGES project focuses on 12 Beacon Regions , we considered it important to include the respectivenational nutritional plans for you to have an idea of what these countries are doing in terms of promoting healthy foods:

- Denmark
- France
- Finland
- Greece
- Ireland
- Italy
- Latvia
- Lithuania
- Netherland
- Poland
- Spain
- Turkey

Changing habits

Some studies revealed that there is an “excessive consumption of calories, saturated fats, trans fats, sugar and salt; as well as low consumption of vegetables, fruits and whole grains; and increasing numbers of people with obesity – all of which not only shorten life expectancy but also harm the quality of life ” (World Health Organization, 2021).

Most people find it difficult to move from an unhealthy diet to a healthy one. Good habits can be learned, and with effort, it is possible to switch to a healthier lifestyle. For this reason, we have included some tips and important aspects of a healthy diet that could help you to adopt this lifestyle. The list is not exhaustive, and it would be best to accompany a healthy diet with physical activity.

Decalogue of a healthy diet:

1 Avoid soft drinks and drink plenty of water

2 Avoid processed meats and avoid eating meat for at least 1 day/week

3 Include at least 50% of fresh products in your meals

4 Eat vegetables and fruits, these should fill half your plate at every meal and snack. Remember not to replace fruits with 100% natural juices as they contain less fibre

5 Choose whole-grain foods instead of processed or refined grains, it is advised to fill a quarter of your plate with whole-grain foods

6 Consume protein-rich foods every day, these should fill a quarter of your plate

7 Avoid ultra-processed foods

8 Buy local products and prepare most of your meals at home, get inspired by seasonal products that you can buy locally

9 Look for new and interesting healthy recipes on the internet and create a calendar of what you will eat each day to make it easier to balance out the food you are eating

10 If you buy packaged food, read the nutritional table to be aware of what you are eating

•Fresh products

These products have a direct impact on the success of short food supply chains, as some consumers tend to buy local food with the motivation to find fresher products than the ones they can buy in supermarkets or other stores .

You can always ask a doctor or dietitian to help you find a healthy diet that is suitable for you. Always remember that your “energy intake (calories) should be in balance with energy expenditure ” (World Health Organization, 2020)

As was explained, an important aspect to be considered is where you buy your food from. Bear in mind that local food will be fresher than the food you buy in grocery stores and supermarkets. We encourage you to prepare a shopping list beforehand and identify where to obtain the products you need. If you buy locally, you can get fresh healthy food , and you will be helping local families. The benefits of buying locally through SFSCs have been discussed in the previous chapter.

Fresh food

It is the one “that is not preserved by canning or dehydration or freezing or smoking”.

Train & Education

Train & Education

As mentioned before, one of the relevant aspects to be considered in relation to SFSCs and local food is raising awareness and educating citizens about healthy habits. To spread the word, it is essential to be knowledgeable about the topics, and that is why the first part of this handbook goes through a series of concepts and relevant information about local food, SFSCs and healthy habits.

This section includes background information about how to teach others. Some tips and materials are included for carrying out knowledge transfer activities.

General information & tips

To start off, it is important to understand what we are referring to when talking about educating others. For the purposes of this section, education is the act or process of imparting or acquiring general knowledge or skills. It implies that someone is an expert or has knowledge about a specific topic (trainer, facilitator, teacher or professor) and that there is another who wants or needs to learn (trainee, learner or student).

The idea is that you have enough information so you can act as a trainer or facilitator and carry out knowledge transfer activities through various means and techniques.

Means and techniques for inspiring and educating others

Teaching and learning can be complex, as each person acquires knowledge in different ways. To ensure that all learners understand a certain content, facilitators must use strategies or teaching methods to improve their performance, adapt the content, motivate learners, and shape knowledge.

Educational methodologies

Set of teaching tools, techniques, strategies and methods that teachers use to increase student participation and ensure an active and meaningful experience in the learning process.

It is important to note that there is no single, most effective methodology. Everything depends, mainly, on the context where it is implemented and on the characteristics of the group. The most important thing is to stimulate the learner, thus seeking to arouse curiosity and in turn the desire to learn.

There are many different techniques used in knowledge transfer activities, but for this handbook, we will focus on trending teaching techniques that actively involve the participant in the learning process:

- **Flipped classroom or inverted classroom:** This technique consists of students studying and preparing the lesson to be discussed, in advance of the class. In this way, students come from home with the basic concepts assimilated and the class can focus on solving any doubts they have about the subject, or what has generated the most curiosity.

- **Gamification (games):** it is probably the most fun technique since it is based on learning through play. Through gamification, the student learns without realising it. The main objective of gamification is to enhance motivation and reinforce student behaviour so that they can solve problems dynamically.

• **Discussions and debates:** This technique implies the audience is involved in the learning process. Students could either be prepared beforehand with information or they could be asked to think about the topic for the first time in class. The choice depends on your objectives and intended outcomes.

• **Interaction through social media networks:** In an age where communication technology is all around us, social networks (social media) can be strong allies for teachers. In this way, students who interact through social networks will have additional motivation to learn. This could go hand in hand with an online discussion or debate or with a communications campaign for raising awareness.

• **Problem-based learning or case study method:** It is an active work technique that focuses on research, learning and reflection to reach the resolution and conclusion of the problem posed. The solution to the problem generates curiosity and promotes creativity, stimulating learning, decision making and argumentation. Each facilitator, in a pedagogical way, must design projects that are suitable for their students, and for that, they must consider age and level of knowledge.

Special attention should be paid to e-learning techniques, as even if the abovementioned techniques can be applied online, the learning process is different. The term e-learning, coined by the education expert Elliott Masie at a conference he offered in 1999, refers to the use of network technology to design, distribute, select, administer and share learning (Cinema8, 2021).

This modality can involve simple educational resources such as videos, articles, podcasts or any other material found on the Internet, to well-structured courses and careers, which makes it have a greater scope. In the “Useful resources & materials” section, you can find materials that can be used in e-learning programmes.

How to be a good facilitator

Apart from the techniques used to spread knowledge, you can also work on your skills and methods to arouse interest.

1 Use technology

There are several digital tools available.

2 Tell a story

People understand and remember stories better than isolated data, so presenting the information through stories can be a very useful technique to explain yourself more clearly.

3 Adapt the way you communicate

Make sure to use clear and accessible language that is appropriate for your audience. When it comes to teaching, age is critical. Adults and children do not learn in the same way or at the same pace, and as teachers, we must know how to adapt to each type of student.

4 Think about your audience

Do not focus on what you would like to learn, but on what your students might be interested in learning.

5 Make it dynamic

Teaching can be made dynamic not only in the way the content is presented, but also by encouraging active participation

Educating children, young learners and adults

There is a difference between we educating young people and adults as they do not learn at the same rate as a child. Their brain is accustomed to consolidated learning, and they are able to understand information that is more complex. the abovementioned means and techniques can result in great knowledge transfer activities if they are adapted to the specific audience.

When attempting to reach adults and young learners, it should be noted that they have less free time than children would. It is therefore best to share the content that is most relevant for them and that will arouse their interest.

As consumers, they would probably be more interested in knowing the benefits they will obtain if they choose to buy local food from SFSCs. To this end, we recommend you use the following structure when sharing knowledge:

1. Using the “SFSC & local food in Europe” section, you can start by explaining key definitions already included in text boxes. You must emphasize the different economic, social and environmental benefits of SFSCs.

3. One of the benefits of local food is that it supports access to healthy food, and that is why you can make use of the information included in the dedicated section of this handbook.

2. You can continue by explaining what local food is , and where to find it through SFSCs . In this handbook, we have included some examples related to specific countries, so if you have any audience from those regions, you may include that information as it will make it easier for them to understand what you are explaining. If you choose to mention the different business models that make local food through SFSCs accessible, we recommend you refer to specific places rather than the models as it would be easier for the audience to remember them. This is with reference to on-farm pick-up, local markets, e-commerce platforms, etc.

This is a basic structure as it presents the information in a summarised way. However, a fully dedicated training session could be organised for each one of the points mentioned. Deciding on the information to focus in on will all depend on the audience.

Children experience two fundamental stages of growth and socialisation within which they learn consumption patterns and how to behave. The first of these is the family, a place where basic functions are learned, such as speaking and eating, in addition to learning the values and social norms that will guide their future. The second is school, following which they emerge to the world where they live amongst their peers and adults, assimilating new knowledge.

Children learn more quickly and strengthen knowledge in an easy way when these two stages work hand in hand. This means that for children to become adults who consume local food from SFSCs, there is a long process which needs to occur at schools and at home with the family.

If children show an interest in sharing their doubts and ideas at home, they are more easily able to learn, and they have more encouragement to participate in classes and extracurricular activities. In addition, when parents are curious about the topics their children are learning, students are able to reaffirm their knowledge even more. Schools and families share the task of educating. For this reason, adults must learn about these topics, both for their own purposes but so that they can teach children.

Although family and schools are the main agents for educating children, the approach each should follow is different. At school, children would need to have all the food-related topics mentioned in the previous section as part of their curriculum. For example, teachers could use gamification techniques and invite kids to participate in some challenges where they need to actively take part in identifying the benefits of local food or healthy diets. If we focus on a family, it would be more important that children are familiar with consumption patterns that include healthy food from SFSCs.

In the “Useful resources” section , you will find customisable images that can be used in the learning process. They can be downloaded here.

Organising knowledge transfer activities – Webinar as a success case

There are many possibilities to teach and inspire others. If you are a school, you can take advantage of the infographics, wordsearch and editable images that we have included in the “Useful resources” section.

If you want to educate young people or adults, we encourage you to watch our webinars on Healthy Diets and Benefits of Local Food as an example of the kind of content you could share, and how to go about it.

In recent years, webinars have become one of the most successful ways to reach higher numbers of audiences with a wide geographical spread. We are therefore including some tips on how to organise webinars as one of the most successful ways to teach others on local food and SFSCs:

The first step is to identify what type of session is most appropriate. We can choose from different structures such as the Mainstage Style, which consists of a welcome or introduction, followed by a core presentation and finishing off with a summary and thanks or administrative remarks .

1. WHAT TYPE OF SESSION DO WE WANT?

W - WELCOME
I - PANELIST INTRODUCTIONS
P - PRESENTATION
MC - MODERATOR-CURATED QUESTIONS DIRECTED TO THE PANELIST
Q & A - QUESTIONS FROM THE AUDIENCE DIRECTED TO A PANELIST(S)
S - SUMMARY
T - THANK YOU/ADMINISTRATIVE REMARKS

If interaction is desired, then there is the option for a Q&A style, which allows time for around 10 questions. The graphic above shows that there are several options available. Some are useful situations with different panellists while others are useful for when there is a moderator to drive the conversation between the panellist and the audience.

It is recommended that you count with the participation of other presenters as it helps in obtaining a larger audience, whilst also making the webinar more interesting as different perspectives are included.

After planning the initial structure, you can look into what type of interaction you would like to have with your audience. You can choose from a workshop style where people participate actively, or use a software or tool to take questions.

For instance, Mentimeter is a popular choice because it is quite simple and it has a freemium version. In addition to building interactive presentations, this software makes it easy to include questions, polls and quizzes. It creates a lot of engagement and participation, is easy to use and can be used independently of any webinar software.

If you would like to go a step further, you can design some exercises or enable the audience to work in groups as it provides for more elaborate insights that can be leveraged for lead generation and classification and usually deliver quite high engagement and user satisfaction rates.

This comes at a higher cost since such activities require significant preparation, and would require the use of paid software tools such as GoToTraining.

A more innovative method for online events is the use of co-creation exercises. They provide similar advantages to working in groups but require a skilful facilitator, solid planning and the use of external tools such as Miro.

At this point, it is possible to select the core software to be used in the session. There are many options available, including Teams, Zoom, GoToMeeting, and others.

You can record the webinar and upload it to Youtube to reach a higher audience and to make it available for people who couldn't attend at the time. If you plan to do this, it is important to notify people that the session is being recorded due to GDPR.

Once the webinar is over, it is recommended to send a follow-up email to all the participants with the session recording, the PowerPoint presentations or PDFs, and the document gathering all the questions and answers from the session.

In conclusion, here are a few ideas to promote your online event or webinar:

- Use a pop-up or slider on your website to promote your event when displaying related information
- Publish relevant content in a blog post or in your news section on your website
- Share it on social media channels
- Email to institutions that may help with dissemination
- Email to stakeholders who may be interested in joining the webinar
- Send a press release to the media

Key concepts

Key concepts

This section includes different definitions and concepts that are relevant to local food, and that will help achieve an understanding of Short Food Supply Chains. Included are also explanations of concepts related to ways of interacting with farmers and purchasing local food.

Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems

The term refers to the “ways people and organisations interact within a country or a region, including farming practices, businesses, authorities, research, etc” (EIP-AGRI Support Facility, 2018)

Agroecological farming

It attempts to “create stable food production systems that are resilient to environmental perturbations such as climate change and disease”. (Shulman, 2020)

Agroecology

This approach “simultaneously applies ecological and social concepts and principles to the design and management of food and agricultural systems. It seeks to optimize the interactions between plants, animals, humans and the environment while taking into consideration the social aspects that need to be addressed for a sustainable and fair food system”. (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2018)

Box scheme

“An arrangement where consumers pay a fixed amount for an agreed quantity of vegetables, fruit or other produce, to be delivered to their home on a regular basis” (Strength2food project, 2020)

Clean label

This includes the ingredient lists, what is advertised on the packaging, and the product’s impact on the environment and people . (Lascom, 2018)

Community Supported Agriculture

Abbreviated to CSA, it is a partnership model between consumers and producers “where consumers share part of the risks, decisions and rewards of production”. (Short Food Supply Chain Network, 2019) Both parties benefit as producers receive stable and secure incomes, while consumers receive access to fresh food.

Consumer

“A person who buys goods or services for their own use” (Cambridge University Press, 2018)

Convenience good

It is an item “that is widely available and purchased frequently with minimal effort” (Kenton, 2021) and it is normally purchased as part of a habit. In this category, we can find goods such as pre-cut vegetables or fast food.

Education

The act or process of imparting or acquiring knowledge (Random House, 2016)

Educational techniques

A set of teaching tools, techniques, strategies and methods that teachers use to increase student participation and ensure an active and meaningful experience in the learning process. (Collins, 2017)

E-learning

“The use of network technology to design, distribute, select, administer and share learnings ” (Cinema8, 2021)

Farm delivery

“Retail market option where consumers receive farm produce delivered to their home”. (Strength2food project, 2020)

Farm shop

“A retail outlet that sells produce directly from a farm”. (Strength2food project, 2020)

Farmers’ cooperative

“A group of farmers that co-operate in certain areas of activities and pool resources, e.g. for production, marketing and retail”. (Strength2food project, 2020)

Farmers’ market

“A physical retail marketplace where farmers can sell their home-grown produce, as well as other processed goods, directly to consumers”. (Strength2food project, 2020)

Farming

“The activity of growing crops or keeping animals on a farm” (Collins, 2017)

Food hub

“A centrally located facility supporting the aggregation, storage, processing, marketing and distribution of locally produced food.” (Strength2food project, 2020)

Food loss

This “occurs before the food reaches the consumer as an unintended result of agricultural processes or technical limitations in the production, storage, processing and distribution stages”. (EAT-Lancet Commission , 2019)

Food miles

The “distance between the place where food is grown or made, and the place where it is eaten ”. (Cambridge University Press, 2019)

Food producer

A “person who grew, raised, processed, prepared, manufactured, or otherwise added value to the food product”. (Law Insider, 2017)

Food system

This includes “all elements and activities that relate to production, processing, distribution, preparation and consumption of food ”. (EAT-Lancet Commission , 2019)

Food waste

It “refers to food fit for consumption that is consciously discarded at the retail and consumption stages ” or food lost post-harvest. (EAT-Lancet Commission , 2019)

Fresh

When used in regard to fruit and vegetables, it refers to those that have not been processed (e.g. canned, pickled, preserved or frozen). (Loades, 2017)

Fresh food

Food “that is not preserved by canning or dehydration or freezing or smoking ”. (IXL Learning, n.d.)

Fresh products

These products have a direct impact on the success of short food supply chains, as some consumers tend to buy local food with the intention of finding fresher products than those they find in supermarkets or other stores (Short Food Supply Chain Network, 2019).

Geographical Indication

This is a “label used on products that have a specific geographical origin and possess qualities or a reputation that are due to that origin”. (World Intellectual Property Organization, 2018)

Green public procurement (GPP) guidelines

GPP is defined in the European Commission’s Communication “Public procurement for a better environment” as a process whereby public authorities seek to procure goods, services and works with a reduced environmental impact throughout their life cycle when compared to goods, services and works with the same primary function that would otherwise be procured. One of the priority sectors identified by the Commission is food and catering (agroBRIDGES Consortium, 2021).

Healthy diets

“Healthy diets have an optimal caloric intake and consist largely of a diverse plant-based foods, low amounts of animal-based foods, contain unsaturated rather than saturated fats, and limited amounts of refined grains, highly processed foods and added sugars”. (EAT-Lancet Commission , 2019)

Intermediary

A person or organization who passes proposals between two people or groups. (Collins, 2021)

Local food

Food that “is produced within a short distance of where it is consumed, often accompanied by a social structure and supply chain different from the large-scale supermarket system”. (Waltz, 2011)

Local community

A group of people within a local geographical area. (Stands4 LLC, 2021)

Local shop

“An independent local business that sells products within a local community”. (Strength2food project, 2020)

Off Farm Sales

Where the product is not sold on the farmer’s premises, but at a nearby location with clear product identification (e.g. farmer s’ markets, food festivals, co-operatives, trustful and close-by HoReCa and retailers). (agroBRIDGES Consortium, 2021)

On farm purchase

“A retail market option where consumers can directly purchase home-grown produce from the farm ”. (Strength2food project, 2020)

On farm sales

Local food is sold directly on the farmer’s or producer’s premises (e.g., farm shops, farm based hospitality, roadside sales and pick-your-own) (agroBRIDGES Consortium, 2021).

Organic farming

This “is an agricultural method that aims to produce food using natural substances and processes ”. Thus, having less impact on the environment. (European Commission, 2021)

Plant-based food

It includes fruits, vegetables, nuts, seeds and wholegrains.

Pick-your-own

“An arrangement where consumers can directly pick fruits and vegetables from a farm, paying an agreed amount based on basket weight / value ”. (Strength2food project, 2020)

Public Procurement

It refers to the “process by which public authorities, such as government departments or local authorities, purchase work, goods or services from companies ”. (European Commission, 2018)

Retailer

“A person or business that sells goods to the public in relatively small quantities for use or consumption rather than for resale ”. (Lexico, 2021)

Sales at distance

This model address types of short food supply chains where food is sold and delivered outside the production region, but information is duly labelled and embedded to be transferred to consumers. Farm direct deliveries via different delivery schemes, internet sales or speciality retailers are included in this type of short food supply chain (agroBRIDGES Consortium, 2021).

Sales in proximity

This model includes both face-to-face sales (where consumers buy directly, trusting in personal interaction) and proximate sales (where food is produced and sold in a given region of production) (agroBRIDGES Consortium, 2021).

Self-service vending machine

“A food distribution option where consumers can purchase fresh produce, supplied by local producers, by filling up their own/provided containers ”. (Strength2food project, 2020)

Short food supply chains (SFSCs)

For the purposes of the agroBRIDGES project a definition was developed and agreed that is clear and easy to understand: Short food supply chains have as few links as possible between the food producer and the consumer/citizen who eats the food.

Solidarity purchasing group

“A group of people, e.g. households, that co-operate in purchasing food and other produce directly from farmers ”. (Strength2food project, 2020)

Supply Chain

It can be defined as the “entire system of producing and delivering a product or service, from the initial stage of sourcing the raw materials to the final delivery of the product or service to end-users ”. (CFI Education, 2021)

Sustainable Food System

It “delivers food security and nutrition for all in such a way that the economic, social and environmental bases to generate food security and nutrition for future generations are not compromised ”. (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2018)

Wholesale

“The business of selling goods in large quantities and at low prices, typically to be sold on by retailers at a profit ”. (Lexico, 2021)

Useful resources & materials

Useful resources & materials

In this section, you will find extra information that may be helpful in case you want to learn more about local food and healthy habits. You will also find communication materials to be used when training others.

Success cases for consumers

Visit our catalogue on Good Practices available on our project website, find the one that best suits your needs through the filters on the right and using the search engine. You will also find within each article a link through which you can see the full content of each good practice. In addition, you can also watch our video including 12 success cases.

Catalogue on Good Practices

Video

FOODS HIGH IN ANTIOXIDANTS

Berries such as
blueberries and
raspberries

Dark leafy
greens

Pumpkin
and carrots

Nuts and
seeds

FOODS RICH IN CALCIUM

Broccoli

Low fat dairy products

Cauliflower

Cabbage

Canned fish with bones

Tofu

Legumes

HIGH GLYCEMIC DIET

A DIET FOR A BRAIN HEALTH CONTAINS

Vitamin D, vitamin C,
and vitamin E

Omega-3
fatty acids

Flavonoids and
polyphenols

Fish

GOOD FOOD FOR A GUT HEALTH

Vegetables

Fruits

Legumes

Whole
grains

Yogurt

Kimchi

Sauerkraut

Miso

kefir

Material for kids

Concepts

Consumer

A person who buys goods or services for their own use

Fresh food

It is the one that has been picked or produced recently, and has not been preserved, for example by being frozen or put in a tin

Healthy diets

It implies eating a variety of foods so that you can get all the nutrients you need for normal growth

Local food

It is the one produced close to the place where you consume it, for example, by a farm near your house

Short food supply chains (SFSCs)

SFSCs reduce the number of intermediaries, such as wholesalers or large supermarket chains, between the farmer and the consumers; for example, food can be sold directly by the farmer on the farm, in farmers market or online, or sold by small local retailers.

Healthy Plate

1/2 VEGETABLES & FRUIT

Choose variety of colors. Green, yellow orange and red are the best choices

WATER

Avoid sugaty drinks

1/4 GRAIN FOOD

Try to avoid refined (white) grains and prefer wole (brown) grains

1/4 PROTEIN

Fish, poultry, nuts, dairy are ideal sources of protein

Word search

You can create your own word search using this link or use the one we have created for you:

Z	P	R	O	D	U	C	E	R	J	M	D
Q	C	O	N	S	U	M	E	R	B	W	I
H	E	K	Z	Q	J	L	Q	A	I	L	F
D	K	P	X	H	I	E	N	S	D	O	X
F	R	Q	G	E	L	S	H	O	O	C	F
P	V	D	O	A	V	Q	A	X	B	A	R
M	D	T	B	L	S	R	M	W	J	L	E
V	I	I	O	T	H	M	N	Z	I	T	S
K	E	U	F	H	O	L	F	O	O	D	H
T	T	B	R	Y	P	J	A	T	U	A	A
U	V	E	G	E	T	A	B	L	E	S	P
J	Z	B	M	J	K	H	M	R	J	P	X

CONSUMER
FOOD
HEALTHY
FRESH
SHOP

PRODUCER
DIET
VEGETABLES
LOCAL

Useful links

Food chain explained to kids

Report on Healthy and Sustainable Diets for European Countries, from the European Public Health Association

Healthy eating check up

Healthy meal planner

Nutrimeter for kids

Finland

- Local Food Programme - Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry
- National information source for local food
- Food related information

France

- Consume fresh and local - Ministry of Agriculture and Food
- Accueil - Ici C Local
- OAD - Decision support tool
- For a healthy and sustainable diet – Report
- Fresh and local, the platform for healthy and responsible eating
- Build your territorial food project to bring local production and local consumption closer
- Territorial anchoring and enhancement of heritage

Greece

- National action plan on food reformulation
- Food-based dietary guidelines

Ireland

- Healthy Eating Guidelines
- Eat well
- Healthy eating
- Irish Food Board

Italy

- Guidelines for healthy eating

Latvia

- List of recommendations of the Ministry of Health (MoH) on healthy nutrition for various groups of society
- Regulations on Nutritional Norms for Students of Educational Institutions, Clients of Social Care and Social Rehabilitation Institutions and Patients of Medical Institutions
- Regulations on the Maximum Permissible Amount of Trans-Fatty Acids in Food Products
- Law on the Circulation of Energy Drinks
- Report on the sustainable mutual cooperation between the public and private sectors for the promotion of a healthy lifestyle for children
- Measures implemented as part of the ESF Health Promotion Project
- On Excise Duty
- Sample menus for educational institutions

Lithuania

- Description of the Procedure for the Organization of Catering in Pre-School Education, General Education in Schools and Social Care Institutions for Children
- Obligations of Food Businesses under the Cooperation Agreement With Sam on Improvement of Foodstuffs
- National Public Health Development Programme
- National Health Strategy 2014-2025
- Order on the Labelling of Foodstuffs
- Regulation on preschool and school nutrition
- Order on the maximum levels for trans fatty acids in foodstuffs

Poland

- Commercial quality and food labelling
- Meet Good Food
- The canon of Polish cuisine
- Poland tastes good
- Polish product
- National food quality systems
- Food promotion strategy
- "Keep in Form!" - educational programme about balanced nutrition and activity
- Healthy eating in schools

Spain

- NAOS_Strategy
- Food-based dietary guidelines
- Policy - Information on the Nutri-Score model]
Global database on the Implementation of
Nutrition Action (GINA)

The Netherlands

- Programs and agreements aiming at healthier diets
- Measures for promoting healthier diets to reduce the occurrence of obesity and overweight
- Reduce the amount of salt, saturated fat and calories (sugar) in products
- Objective information about healthy diets
- Tips to people for a healthier lifestyle
- Healthier diets as a way to prevent disease / protect human health
- National institute for public health and environment

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Annex

Annex I - Factsheets - Status of SFSCs in
different countries

ANDALUSIA, SPAIN.

- POPULATION: **8,427 MILLION** (2019)

- REPRESENTING **36,9%** OF THE OVERALL SPANISH GROSS ADDED VALUE IN THE AGRICULTURE SECTOR.

FRUITS AND VEGETABLES:

- 21,872 OF PRODUCERS
- IT HAS 4,400 MILLION OF HECTARE
- 124,921 HECTARES (FRUIT'S LAN)
- 2,66 MILLION OF TONNES (FRUIT'S PRODUCTION VOLUME (2019))
- 3,013 MILLION (36,4% OF THE TOTAL SPANISH PRODUCTION VALUE)
- 122,072 HECTARES (VEGETABLE LAND 2019)
- 6,50 MILLION OF TONNES (VEGETABLE PRODUCTION VOLUME 2019)
- 3,319 MILLION (49,8 % OF TOTAL SPANISH PRODUCTION VALUE)

WHAT IS A SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN?

ECOLOGIC AND CERTIFIED VEGETABLE LOCAL PRODUCTION

- Offer local clients seasonal vegetables, ecologically produced, with low and respectful impact on the environment.
- A tailored system for order placement is usually established. In this case, the clients have the option to order a basket full of ecologic products, having the option to choose the kind of products for the basket or a premade one.

ICT BIDIRECTIONAL PLATFORM AS COMMERCIALISATION CHANNEL

- A platform which issues and control labeled agri-food products, the company identifies Short Food Supply Chain agri-food products and acts as a channel for producers and consumers.
- Producers can publish their products on the platform, add the NATURCODE's QR tag to their products and the customer can look for them on the platform.

FRUITS AND VEGETABLES

TURNOVER OF THE FOOD INDUSTRY: PROCESSING AND PRESERVING OF FRUIT AND VEGETABLES (2020)

- 435,437,000 € (2017)
- 504,684,000 € (2019)

PERCENTAGE OF ORGANICALLY FARMED AREA OF THE TOTAL AREA OF PRODUCTION 13,5% (2019)

OUTDOOR CULTIVATION AREA (2020):

- 19,861 HECTARES
- GREENHOUSE AREA 386 HECTARES.

DAIRY

MANUFACTURE OF DAIRY PRODUCTS (2020)

- 2,23,102,000 € (2017)
- 2,299,744,000 € (2019)

MILK PRODUCTION IN 2019: 2,305 MIL. LITERS

- BUTTER PRODUCTION 51 MIL. KG
- CHEESE 84 MIL. KG

MILK IS MAINLY SOLD TO DAIRIES, WITH ABOUT 4% OF DAIRY FARMS SELLING DIRECTLY TO CONSUMERS (2020).

WHAT IS A SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN?

SELF-PICKING

Self-picking is very valuable model for berry farmers to sell their products. Self-picking is cheaper than buying ready-picked products from the farm or stores as well as higher quality.

Farmer's market sales is an important channel for individual companies, part of the local culture and local food culture.

The local food collectives (incl. REKO) offers consumers a way of ordering products directly from the producer, without the need for middlemen. The REKO collectives operate via Facebook as closed groups in which orders and deliveries are agreed on.

DIRECT SALES

Milk is mainly sold to dairies, with about 4% of dairy farms selling directly to consumers. Some small cheese factories sell their products directly for consumers or HoReCa sector.

FRUITS & VEGETABLES

PRODUCERS IN 2019:

- 30,900 (HORTICULTURE FARMS) • 27,600 (FRUITS FARMIN)
- 21% OF FRENCH FARMS ARE SELLING IN SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN.
- 2,44 MILLION TONNES OF FRESH FRUIT PER YEAR; 5,3 MILLION TONS OF FRESH VEGETABLES/YEAR.
- THE WHOLE PRODUCTION IS ESTIMATED TO BE 44,7 BILLION WORTH IN SALES REVENUE AND 14,3% COME FROM FRUITS AND VEGETABLE PRODUCTION.
- 2019: 4TH BIGGEST PRODUCER OF FRUITS IN EU
- 2018: 3RD BIGGEST PRODUCER OF VEGETABLES IN EU

CEREALS

- 300,000 FARMS OF CEREALS CROPS (2019)
- STATISTICS CONCERNING THE NUMBER OF SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN FOR CEREALS AREN'T AVAILABLE FOR THE MOMENT.
- 66 MILLION TONNES OF CEREALS PRODUCED. (2019)
- CEREAL PRODUCTION MAKES UP FOR 24,2% OF THE SALES REVENUE OF THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR.
- FRANCE IS THE BIGGEST PRODUCER OF CEREALS IN THE EU, THE 3RD PRODUCER IN THE WORLD BEHIND CHINA AND THE USA.

WHAT IS A SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN?

OPEN-AIR MARKETS

Open-air markets are the traditional type of Short Food Supply Chain in France.

- Historical marketplaces, mainly located in the heart of cities, a showcase of a great range of products, well accessible for consumers, pre-existing infrastructures...
- A stable marketplace that facilitates the exchange between the consumer and the producer.
- It's a mature, well-established model that requires a few subtle changes (logistics, price for the rent of a marketplace, timeslot accessibility for families) in order to stimulate more effectively the Short Food Supply Chains.

DIRECT SALES ON FARMS

Direct sales on farms, helped by digital platforms that identify the closest farms to the consumer.

- Easier for producers as they can sell directly where they produce goods, empowerment of producers, the consumer feels more engaged as it provides a better understanding of the origins of the product.
- The key value is the absence of an intermediary.
- A mature model that struggled with the geographical distance between the producer and the consumer but improved thanks to digital platforms making connexions.

FRUITS & VEGETABLES

- **68,811** (HOLDINGS 2016)
- **1,061,226 TONNES**
(FRUIT PRODUCTION VOLUME 2018)
- **201,600 TONNES** (VEGETABLE PRODUCTION 2018)
- **€ 1,094,9 MILLION** (INCOME 2018)
- **46%** (SHARE IN AGRICULTURAL OUTPUT OF THE REGION 2018)

SHEEP SECTOR

- **4,798** (HOLDINGS 2016)
- **123,784 TONNES**
(SHEEP MILK PRODUCTION VOLUME 2018)
- **€ 34,63 MILLION** (INCOME 2018)
- **7%** (SHARE IN ANIMAL OUTPUT OF THE REGION 2018)

WHAT IS A SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN?

OPEN-AIR ORGANIC FARMERS MARKET

- Consumer purchases a product directly from the local producer or wholesaler on a face-to-face basis.
- Based on the traditional and well-established model of open-air markets.
- Contributing to and satisfying the consumers quest for healthy and safe products at fair prices.
- Establishing trust regarding the quality of the products offered.
- A collective, bottom-up, endogenous process of initiating and implementing change in food systems (conventional versus organic).

SOCIAL CONSUMER COOPERATIVE

- Products are produced and retailed in the specific region of production.
- Products mainly come from local areas of proximity, so that closer relationship with the producers is maintained and transport costs are minimised.
- Any interested individual can be member of the cooperative by paying a subscription fee.
- Members participate in the selection of the type and quality of products to be sold and the negotiations about the prices.
- Honesty and trust are created by the social character of the model.

-IRELAND

-POPULATION: **4,977,400**

-AGRI-FOOD AND TOURISM ARE CRITICAL TO RURAL ECONOMIES IN IRELAND AND BETWEEN THEM EMPLOY IN 2017 IS **363,000 (18%)** OF THE WORKFORCE

BEEF

- **78,300** SPECIALIST BEEF CATTLE FARMS
- TOTAL BEEF PRODUCTION: **520,000** TONNES
- EXPORTATIONS: **470,000** TONNES
- **5TH LARGEST NET** EXPORTER OF BEEF IN THE WORLD
- BEEF WORTH ALMOST **€2.5 BILLION** WAS EXPORTED TO AROUND 70 COUNTRIES IN 2018
- IRISH BEEF PRODUCTION IS PREDOMINATELY A GRASS-BASED SYSTEM, WITH **617 THOUSAND TONNES** PRODUCED IN 2017.

HORTICULTURE

- IRELAND'S HORTICULTURE SECTOR HAD A FARM GATE VALUE OF **€477 MILLION** (2019)
- **4TH HIGHEST** SECTOR IN TERMS OF GROSS AGRICULTURAL COMMODITY OUTPUT VALUE
- MUSHROOMS ACCOUNTED FOR **€119.2M** WITH POTATOES **€111M**, FIELD VEGETABLES **€77.8M**, PROTECTED CROPS **€91.5M** AND OUTDOOR FRUIT **€10.7M**
- THE MUSHROOM INDUSTRY IS THE LARGEST HORTICULTURAL SECTOR IN IRELAND WITH A FARM GATE VALUE OF **€119 MILLION**
- IN 2019 THERE WERE 34 MUSHROOM GROWERS PRODUCING OVER **68,000 TONNES**. THE SECTOR EMPLOYS APPROX. 3,500 PEOPLE.

WHAT IS A SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN?

NEIGHBOURFOODS

• Through this website, a consumer can find their local market on the markets page and choose from a wide range of local produce including fruit and veg, bread, pastries, cheese, meats, beers and many more. Purchases are made online. Each week consumers collect their order at a local venue. At the collection, all items are packed and ready to be collected. All of the products listed in a NeighbourFood market are grown or produced by local farmers or artisan producers.

The sale of any large-scale commercially grown vegetables, non-organic imported fruit or vegetables, genetically modified products, intensively reared meat, imported fish or battery eggs are not permitted to be sold at a NeighbourFood market.

SPECIALISED RETAIL SHOP

• The Little Cheese Shop is a small retail shop that sells mostly local cheese but also a few high-quality cheeses from overseas. The cheese is purchased directly from the producer. The company has one local shop and an online shop. Product range is a minimum of 90% Irish but is generally at around 95%. The imported produce is top of the range foreign produce (for example a cheese shop must sell parmesan, so they import the best parmesan cheese).

Good quality cheeses are sold with expert advice and knowledge on the products from the retailer. The shop supports local farmers.

To be a direct link - they offer a link for new products to get into the market. Where the producers can't be there in person, they have a spokesperson for them.

-9,994,006
(POPULATION 2021)

-€30,035 MILLION
(FOOD INDUSTRY)

-€61,6 BILLION
(AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY, AND FISHERIES PRODUCTION)

FRUITS & VEGETABLES

- 864,860 HECTARES (2020)
- 30,146,182 QUINTALS (PRODUCTION 2020)
- 27 PRODUCTS WITH GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATION
- 40 (PRODUCER ORGANIZATIONS 2020)
- 40,000 (EMPLOYEES IN VEGETABLES PRODUCTION 2020)
- 15,000 (FRUIT FARMS 2020)

BEEF SECTOR

- €430 MILLION PER YEAR
- 282,000 (ANIMALS REGISTERED IN THE HERD BOOK 2019)
- 8,000 BREEDING FARMS
- COALVI CONSORTIUM BRINGS TOGETHER MORE THAN 1,500 FARMS
- PRODUCER - BUTCHERS - CONSUMER (SHORT SUPPLY CHAIN)

WHAT IS A SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN?

FARMERS' MARKETS

The model allows producers to sell their products directly to consumers in physical spaces dedicated to them. Generally, in Farmers' Markets, there are several stalls, each of which is occupied by a farmer that offers its products. In the Farmer's Market, all foodstuffs are sold, from fruit and vegetables to meat, from wine to oil, from fish to processed products.

The reasons that most drive consumers to get supplies are the high quality of the products, the direct contact with the producers, thus having the opportunity to learn about their stories and their production techniques, and the possibility of supporting the local agricultural economy.

ALLIANCE AMONG OPERATORS AND COALVI CONSORTIUM

The model is based on the specificity of products and services offer to customers. It is a kind of faith agreement between sellers and customers. On the one side, the key points are quality, local origin, and service; on the other side, the key elements are continuity/fidelity in the purchases and willingness to pay a high price differential.

Relations with consumers are managed through personal contacts, that is the leverage point of this model. It is a personal and social relationship, based on trust.

-NETHERLANDS

-POPULATION: **17,3 MILLION**

-THE DUTCH AGRICULTURAL SECTOR EXPORTS AROUND
€ 65 BILLION OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCE ANNUALLY.

HORTICULTURE

-**2069** (PRODUCERS)

-TOTAL PRODUCTION VALUE SHORT FOOD
SUPPLY CHAIN: **€ 2691 MILLION**

-SHARE IN TOTAL PLANT-BASED AGRICULTURAL
PRODUCTION: **18,9%**

DAIRY

-**1146** (PRODUCERS)

-TOTAL PRODUCTION VALUE SHORT FOOD
SUPPLY CHAIN: **€ 196 MILLION**

-SHARE IN TOTAL ANIMAL-BASED
AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION: **1,8%**

WHAT IS A SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN?

DIRECT SALES – RECHTSTREEX

Rechtstreex provides an online platform where consumers can order local agri-food products. After the orders have been collected, local producers are informed, and the food products are picked up and transported to the distribution centres from Rechtstreex. From there the products are sent to regional pick-up points where consumers can collect their orders.

Key elements: online orders by consumers, assortment of fresh food products (large variety of products, from meat and dairy to fresh fruits and vegetables to bakery products and snacks), distribution and logistics coordinated by Rechtstreex, pick-up points in neighbourhoods where orders are placed, deliveries / pick-up by consumers twice per week.

STREECKGENOTEN

Streeckgenoten is a quality label that identifies local and specialty food products from local producers. The labelled products are sold in one of the main Dutch supermarket chains (Albert Heijn) and hence has a wide coverage throughout the Netherlands.

Local products sold in supermarkets allows consumers to buy local while doing one-stop shopping for their household. The success of the model is due to the potential for scaling and efficient logistics and distribution through supermarkets.

PIGS

THE PIG POPULATION IS **13 MILLION**. IN 2016, WE EXPORTED PORK FOR ALMOST 4 BILLION EUR.

THE PRODUCTION OF PIGS GIVES A CONTRIBUTION TO GDP IN THE REGION OF **€2,5 BILLION**.

CEREALS

APPROX. 1400 HECTARES ARE USED FOR GRAIN PRODUCTION AND 9.6 MILLION TONNES ARE HARVESTED PER YEAR.

USUALLY MORE THAN 70 % IS USED FOR FEED AND A FURTHER 15-20 % GOES TO EXPORT. THE REST IS DISTRIBUTED ON SEEDS, FLOUR, AND GROATS AS WELL AS FOR INDUSTRIAL CONSUMPTION (INCLUDING BEER). DENMARK IS TYPICALLY A NET EXPORTER OF GRAIN.

WHAT IS A SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN?

FARM SHOPS

Farm shops are spread all over rural areas of Denmark. They sell produce from the farm - maybe supplemented with goods from the surrounding farms.

The farm shop taps into the consumers desire for authentic, fresh, healthy and local products. You can talk to the farmer and see the production. It gives a sense of security to know where, how and by whom the goods are produced.

Many farm shops combine the shop with experience-based initiatives such as a tour of the farm, courses in preparing the ingredients, pick-your-own events, etc. There are also some of the farms that combine the shop with a café or restaurant. Several have also combined with a web shop.

FOOD COMMUNITIES

Food Communities is a fairly new and innovative approach to SFSC. They buy (often organic) products directly from local producers, delivered to the members of the food community.

The food communities are run by volunteers, and all members put volunteer hours into the operation and development of the food community. The members of a food community are therefore not just members, they are also co-owners and employees. In return for members' contributions to the food community, they can purchase products through the food community.

They establish a close relationship and collaboration with the farmers.

CEREALS

**PRODUCTION 23,000 TONNES
29.8% OF AGRICULTURAL
0,6% OF PRODUCTION VALUE IN EU.
MAINLY - WHEAT AND SPELT AND
BARLEY.**

DAIRY PRODUCTS

**MILK – PRODUCTION 790,000 TONNES
CHEESE- PRODUCTION 51,000 TONNES
22.2% OF AGRICULTURAL NATIONAL VALUE
0.4% OF PRODUCTION VALUE IN EU**

WHAT IS A SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN?

FARMERS' MARKETS

They provide additional food supplies apart from everyday shopping in retail chains or other shops.

In big cities, markets operate every day, in small settlements farmers' markets are for example, once in two weeks.

This is the most popular and go-to business model for every small farmer and producer.

Farmers' markets are often combined with cultural events and provides much-needed face-to-face communication between customers and producers.

ONLINE DISTRIBUTION

Online distribution directly to customers is not a typical model for small farmers and producers only. Lately, large food producers of the agricultural industry have also established e-shops providing delivery of their products directly from factories.

The model is relatively new and is intensively growing as food e-shopping is gaining traction induced by the COVID-19 crisis.

The model caters to the needs of urban residents as it allows them to get fresh produce without investing too much time by physically visiting farmers' markets or shops. Also, it is easy to make baskets with a range of products or choose already assembled baskets thus cutting downtime even more.

FARMLAND COMPRISES 60%, AGRICULTURE IS CHARACTERIZED BY ONGOING CHANGE IN FARM STRUCTURE WITH A 25% INCREASE IN THE AVERAGE FARM SIZE SINCE 2005 AND AVERAGE 4.5% ANNUAL GROWTH IN THE VALUE OF PRODUCTION/HOLDING.

GROSS VALUE ADDED IN 2020: €1,503 MIL

CEREALS

**PRODUCTION 101,000 TONNES
31.3%% OF TOTAL PRODUCTION
1.5% OF PRODUCTION VALUE IN EU.
MAINLY - WHEAT AND SPELT.**

FRUITS AND VEGETABLES

**PRODUCTION 97,000 TONNES
3.6% OF THE TOTAL OF PRODUCTION
0,1% OF PRODUCTION VALUE IN EU.**

WHAT IS A SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN?

MOBILE FARMERS MARKET

Mobile farmer markets are mobile and temporary marketplaces operating in various cities of Lithuania, offering traditional Lithuanian food directly to customers and serving different city districts on different days of the week.

Those markets are mostly located near to supermarkets or public administration buildings and are present in the biggest cities, such as Vilnius, Kaunas, Klaipeda and Šiauliuose. In this business model, the local farms benefit from direct sales to cities/communities that would otherwise lack access to their products.

GOURMET MARKETPLACE

Gourmet marketplaces are gathering representatives from Lithuanian farms and traders of the world's gourmet products under one roof. The market is composed by stores and world kitchens. It links food products and restaurants with consumers, offering a convenient place to buy straight from the farm at a convenient time.

In terms of food products, buyers can purchase fresh n vegetables, dairy products, cheeses, the highest quality of various meat and its products, fish and seafood, grocery products, nuts and dried fruits, warm bread, gourmet products from all over the world, confectionery and beverages.

For culinary experience-oriented customers, the market offers a variety of snack bars and restaurants serving different food - from the freshest pastries, pies and other delicacies to burgers and grill dishes, among others. Additionally, food marketplaces are serving as a way of revitalization / reconstruction of old - often historic - buildings.

DATA THAT CAN SHOW THE IMPORTANCE OF AGRICULTURE/FOOD SECTOR IN THE REGION 51.2% IS RURAL AND AGRICULTURE IS ONE OF THE PROMINENT POLISH SECTORS, PRODUCING 15.4 MILLION HA A VARIETY OF AGRICULTURAL, HORTICULTURAL, AND ANIMAL ORIGIN PRODUCTS

GROSS VALUE ADDED IN 2020: €11,045 MILLION

CEREALS

**PRODUCTION 1,115,000 TONNES
14,7% OF PRODUCTION VALUE
7,8% OF PRODUCTION VALUE IN THE EU MAINLY WHEAT AND SPELT**

FRUITS AND VEGETABLES

**PRODUCTION 141,000 TONNES
31,3% OF AGRICULTURAL NATIONAL VALUE
LARGEST (25%) PRODUCER OF APPLES IN EU REACHING 3.9 MILLION TONES**

WHAT IS A SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN?

DIRECTLY FROM THE FARM

Customers can buy fresh products directly from the farmer. It is the best solution for those who want to know the exact origin of food. They can see the farm, and meet the farmer.

It works both, for a farm located close to (or in) town and also for some distance. There are informal groups to buy and to deliver from the farm once a week or fortnight.

Customers also have the opportunity to meet agricultural producers face to face. They can also take part in tasting products and testing new ones - introduced to the market.

SPECIALISED INTERNET PLATFORM AS A MARKETPLACE

The business model is based on the use of ICT for direct sales. Specially designed websites and social media are used for this. The business model is based on the assumption of minimizing the costs of reaching the target customer with the offer.

Also in this marketing model, the aspects of the freshness of products and their "Polish" origin are emphasized. The slogan "local producer" is a keyword in building the recognition of a commercial offer.

The use of social media is one of the optimal solutions for those who want to know exactly where the food comes from. This solution is true both for farms located close to (or in) the city, as well as for some distant ones, however, it requires greater integration of producers and building common brands.

FRUITS & VEGETABLES

KEREVITAŞ IS ONE OF TURKEY'S LEADING FOOD MANUFACTURERS. IT IS AMONG THE LARGEST PRODUCERS OF FROZEN FOOD, CANNED FISH AND CANNED VEGETABLES. IT IS THE LEADER OF THE FROZEN FOOD INDUSTRY WITH ITS SUPERFRESH BRAND. KEREVITAŞ IS ALSO A PIONEER IN EXPORTS WITH ITS SUPERFRESH BRAND.

THE TOTAL NUMBER OF CONTRACTED FARMERS IS 500 PEOPLE.

- PRODUCTION: 137,000 TONS
- POTATO: 75,000 TONS
- CORN: 38.000 TONS
- PEAS: 4500 TONS
- SPINACH: 3,000 TONS
- GREEN BEANS: 1584 TONS
- ONION: 4,300 TONS
- CARROTS: 1.700 TONS

WHAT IS A SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN?

TYPICAL SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN MODEL FOR THIS BR EX1

Eskitadında.com, which started its operations in January 2017, is a platform that offers the opportunity to sell organic agricultural products directly from the producer to the consumer.

The aim of Eski Tadında is to plant without using chemicals and artificial fertilizers and to prepare products without using any additives such as preservatives, flavorings, shelf life extenders, artificial sweeteners.

For this purpose, agricultural practices of 1920-30s were examined and these practices are applied again in today's conditions. While preparing the product, these methods are used in the production process, just as the product was prepared without using additives in the past.

It carries out all stages of planting, harvesting, preparation and packaging of agricultural products in their old taste. On the other hand, it offers the opportunity to sell the products over the internet so that they can be reached from every region.

TYPICAL SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN MODEL FOR THIS BR EX2

100% Ecological Markets, which started to be established with the cooperation of the Wheat Association and Şişli Municipality in 2006 in Şişli, Feriköy, with 45 stalls and 25 producers, has brought the certified products of approximately 900 fresh fruit and vegetable producers to its buyers until today.

Providing service to an average of 5 thousand households per week only in Istanbul, 100% Ecological Markets continue to be the address of healthy and reliable shopping for 14 years. Within the framework of the applications made in 2019, 24 organic agricultural producers had the chance to deliver their products to their customers by becoming stall holders in 100% Ecological Markets in Istanbul.

The evaluations made in the fall of 2019 by the market commissions, which pay attention to the increase of the producers selling only their own products in the markets, have been concluded. In this context, with the new producers participating in 2020, 100% Ecological Markets have become a more fertile and colorful sharing space.

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